

Conductometric Investigations on Samarium Soaps

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The critical micelle concentration, degree of dissociation and dissociation constant of samarium soaps (valerate, caproate, caprylate and caprate) in a mixture of 60% benzene and 40% methanol were determined by using conductometric measurements. The soaps behaved as simple electrolyte in dilute solutions and the CMC was found to decrease with increasing chainlength of the fatty acid constituent of the soap.

THE survey of literature reveals that the lanthanide and actinide soaps have not yet been thoroughly investigated although these soaps have found wide applications. The physicochemical characteristics and structure of these soaps largely depend on the method and conditions of their preparation. Lanthanide soaps are prepared by double decomposition¹ and metathesis². Mehrotra *et al.*³ reviewed the methods of preparation and properties of lanthanide soaps while Chatfield⁴ summarised the properties and uses of cerium and thorium soaps. Lorant⁵ studied the thermal behaviour of uranyl and thorium soaps. The studies on *ir*, solubility, entropy, apparent heat of solution and detergency of cerium soaps were carried out by several workers⁶. Mehrotra *et al.*⁷ investigated various physicochemical properties of lanthanide and actinide soaps in solid state as well as in solutions.

The present paper deals with the determination of CMC, degree of dissociation and dissociation constant of samarium soaps (valerate, caproate, caprylate and caprate) in a mixture of 60% benzene and 40% methanol by conductivity measurement. The samarium soaps have low solubilities in pure solvents and so the investigations were carried out in the solvent mixture of benzene and methanol.

Experimental

Samarium nitrate hexahydrate (Indian Rare Earths Ltd.) and fatty acids (B.D.H.) were used for the preparation of samarium soaps. The soaps were prepared by direct metathesis of the corresponding potassium soaps with slight excess of aqueous solution of samarium nitrate at 50–55° under vigorous stirring. The precipitated soaps were filtered off and washed with distilled water and alcohol. The soaps were recrystallised with a mixture of benzene and methanol and dried under reduced pressure. The absence of hydroxyl group in soaps was confirmed from their *ir* spectra. The melting points of samarium valerate, caproate, caprylate and caprate were 89, 95, 102 and 105°, respectively. The results of elemental analysis are

in close agreement with the calculated values (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF SAMARIUM SOAPS

Soap	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
	C	H	Metal
Valerate	13.27	1.97	33.09
	(13.22)	(1.98)	(33.16)
Caproate	14.51	2.22	30.31
	(14.52)	(2.22)	(30.32)
Caprylate	16.51	2.58	25.94
	(16.55)	(2.59)	(25.92)
Caprate	18.10	2.86	22.64
	(18.07)	(2.86)	(22.64)

Solutions of different concentrations (± 0.0002 g l⁻¹) of soap were made by adding required amount of benzene and methanol.

A Toshniwal CL 01.10A digital conductivity meter and a dipping type conductivity cell with platinized electrodes were used for measuring the conductance of solutions at a constant temperature of $40 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

Specific conductance, (k) : The specific conductance of the solutions of samarium soaps (valerate, caproate, caprylate and caprate) in a mixture of 60% benzene and 40% methanol (v/v) increases with increasing soap concentration and decreasing chainlength of fatty acid constituent of soap (Fig. 1). The increase in the specific conductance with the increase in soap concentration may be due to the ionisation of samarium soaps into simple metal cations, Sm²⁺ and fatty acid anions, RCOO⁻ (where R is C₄H₉, C₆H₁₁, C₇H₁₃ and C₈H₁₅ for valerate, caproate, caprylate and caprate, respectively) in dilute solutions and due to the formation of micelles at higher soap concentrations. The decrease in specific conductance with increasing chainlength of soap may be due to the increasing size and decreasing mobility of anions with increasing chainlength of soap. The plots of specific

Fig. 1. Plots of specific conductance vs concentration : (○) valerate, (○) caproate, (●) caprylate and (▲) caprate.

conductance vs soap concentration (Fig. 1) are characterised by two breaks corresponding to CMC(I) and CMC(II) of samarium soaps. The appearance of the two breaks can be explained on the basis of formation of ionic and neutral micelles in these soap solutions. It is suggested that the soap is considerably ionised in dilute solutions and the anions begin to aggregate to form ionic micelles at CMC(I). The soaps are largely present in the form of ionic micelles at moderate concentrations (between CMC (I) and CMC (II)) and there is an increasing formation of neutral micelles at CMC(II). The increase of specific conductance with increasing soap concentrations above CMC(II) is mainly due to the liberation of ions from neutral micelles. The values of CMC(I) and CMC(II) were found to decrease with the increase in number of carbon atoms in the soap (Table 3).

Molar conductance (μ) and dissociation constant (K): The molar conductance (μ) of the dilute solutions of samarium soaps in a mixture of 60% benzene and 40% methanol (v/v) decreases with the increase in soap concentration (Table 2). The decrease in molar conductance may be due to the combined effects of ionic atmosphere, solvation of

TABLE 2—CONDUCTANCE OF SAMARIUM VALERATE IN A MIXTURE OF 60% BENZENE AND 40% METHANOL.

Sl. no.	C g mol dm ⁻³	k × 10 ⁴ Ω ⁻¹	μ Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹ (g-mol) ⁻¹ dm ³	α	K × 10 ⁴
1.	0.100 0	42.5	0.425	0.366	7.64
2.	0.088 8	37.1	0.445	0.384	5.51
3.	0.071 4	33.0	0.462	0.398	4.10
4.	0.062 4	29.8	0.478	0.412	3.21
5.	0.055 5	27.8	0.501	0.432	2.83
6.	0.049 9	24.9	0.499	0.480	2.01
7.	0.045 4	23.1	0.509	0.489	1.67
8.	0.041 6	21.7	0.522	0.450	1.45
9.	0.035 7	19.3	0.541	0.466	1.08
10.	0.031 2	17.3	0.554	0.478	0.82
11.	0.027 7	15.8	0.570	0.491	0.66
12.	0.024 9	14.7	0.590	0.509	0.57
13.	0.022 6	13.7	0.606	0.522	0.48
14.	0.020 7	12.9	0.623	0.537	0.43
15.	0.019 1	12.2	0.639	0.551	0.39
16.	0.017 7	11.6	0.655	0.565	0.35
17.	0.016 5	11.1	0.673	0.580	0.33
18.	0.015 4	10.7	0.695	0.599	0.32
19.	0.014 3	10.1	0.706	0.609	0.28
20.	0.013 8	9.7	0.729	0.628	0.27
21.	0.011 8	9.1	0.771	0.665	0.26
22.	0.011 7	8.8	0.793	0.684	0.26
23.	0.010 0	8.4	0.840	0.724	0.27
24.	0.009 1	8.0	0.879	0.758	0.28

TABLE 3—DIFFERENT VALUES OF SAMARIUM SOAPS

Soap	CMC		μ_0	K^* $\times 10^5$	K'^{**} $\times 10^5$	A
	I	II				
Valerate	0.043	0.074	1.16	2.77	1.26	5
Caproate	0.036	0.073	1.03	2.47	1.20	13
Caprylate	0.034	0.071	0.94	1.63	0.60	15
Caprate	0.033	0.066	0.84	1.14	0.50	20

* $K = 27 \times \text{Intercept}/\mu_0^3$. **From the plots of $-\log K$ vs $\sqrt{\alpha C}$.

ions, decrease of mobility and ionisation, and formation of micelles. The plots of μ vs square-root of soap concentration are not linear, which indicates that these soaps behave as weak electrolyte. The limiting conductance (μ_0) can not be obtained by the usual extrapolation method, and Debye-Hückel-Onsager equation is not applicable to these soap solutions. The molar conductance of the solutions of samarium soaps increases with decreasing chain-length of fatty acid constituent of soap but the nature of the curves for these soap solutions remains the same.

The soap in dilute solutions behaves as a simple electrolyte and so an expression for the dissociation of samarium soaps can be developed in Ostwald's manner. If C is the concentration (g mol dm^{-3}) and α is the degree of dissociation of samarium soap, the equivalent concentrations of different species can be represented as

where, R is C_4H_9 , C_5H_{11} , C_7H_{13} and C_9H_{19} for valerate, caproate, caprylate and caprate, respectively. The dissociation constant (K) can be expressed as

$$K = \frac{[\text{Sm}^{3+}][\text{RCOO}^-]^3}{[\text{Sm(RCOO)}_3]}$$

$$= \frac{C\alpha(3C\alpha)^3}{C(1-\alpha)}$$

$$= \frac{27C^3\alpha^4}{(1-\alpha)} \quad (1)$$

Since the ionic concentrations are low and the interionic effects are almost negligible in dilute solution, the solutions of soaps will not deviate appreciably from ideal behaviour and so the activities of ions can be taken as almost equal to the concentrations. The degree of dissociation may be replaced by the conductance ratio, μ/μ_0 , where μ is the molar conductance at finite concentration and μ_0 is the limiting molar conductance at infinite dilution. On substituting the value of α and rearranging, equation (1) can be written as

$$\mu^3 C^3 = \frac{K \mu_0^3}{27\mu} - \frac{K \mu_0^3}{27} \quad (2)$$

The plots of $\mu^3 C^3$ vs $1/\mu$ show that the values of $\mu^3 C^3$ increases slowly and linearly in dilute solutions but increases rapidly in concentrated solutions. The values of dissociation constant (K) and limiting molar conductance (μ_0) have been obtained from the slope, $(K \mu_0^3/27)$ and intercept $(-K \mu_0^3/27)$ of the linear portion of the plots of $\mu^3 C^3$ vs $1/\mu$ for dilute soap solutions and are recorded in Table 3. The values of μ_0 and K decrease with the increase in the chainlength of the soap.

The values of α at different soap concentrations have been calculated by assuming it as equal to the μ/μ_0 . The plots of degree of dissociation vs soap concentration show that the degree of dissociation of these soaps decreases rapidly in dilute solutions with the increase in soap concentration. The values of K calculated by using equation (1) and assuming the degree of dissociation as equal to the conductance ratio are presented in Table 2. The values show that K decreases with increasing chainlength of the soap. The values of K show approximately constancy in dilute solutions but exhibit a drift with increasing soap concentrations which shows that the soap does not behaves as a very weak electrolyte. The drift in the values of dissociation constant with increasing soap concentration may be partly due to the fact that the degree of dissociation, is not exactly equal to the conductance ratio, μ/μ_0 and mainly due to the fact that the activity coefficients of ions are not equal to unity. The deviations at higher soap concentration may also be due to the failure of simple Debye-Hückel activity equation. The dissociation constant, K' of samarium soaps, when the activity coefficient of ions are not equal to unity can be expressed as

$$K' = \frac{27C^3\alpha^4}{(1-\alpha)} \cdot \frac{f_+ f_-^3}{f_{\text{soap}}}$$

where, f_+ , f_- and f_{soap} are activity coefficients of cation, anion and soap, respectively. If the ionic strength is not too high, the activity coefficient of non-ionised molecules of soap, i.e. f_{soap} may be taken as unity. Using Debye-Hückel limiting law for activity coefficients, K' can be expressed as

$$\log K = \log K' + A \sqrt{C\alpha}$$

The values of $\log K$ for samarium soaps are almost constant for dilute solutions but decrease linearly above 0.014 M soap concentration (Fig. 2). The values of K' and A (Table 3) have been obtained from the intercept and slope of the plots of $\log K$ vs $\sqrt{C\alpha}$ for dilute solutions (0.014 M). The values of A increase while the values of K' decrease with increasing chainlength of the soap. The accuracy of K' is ± 0.01 .

The results show that the soap behaves as a simple electrolyte in dilute solutions below the CMC and the conductance results can be explained on the basis of Ostwald's formula and Debye-Hückel theory of electrolytes.

Fig. 2. Plots of $\log K$ vs $(Ca)^{1/2}$ of samarium soaps: (○) valerate, (⊕) caproate, (●) caprylate and (Δ) caprate.

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